

A MODEL FOR INCREASING INCOME AND PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN THE CONTEXT OF OPTIMAL CRITERIA FOR THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF PEASANT FARMS.

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Abstract. This article proposes a modeling approach to evaluate production and income indicators based on optimality criteria to improve the economic efficiency of dehqan farms. Using the example of the Kashkadarya region, a multifactor regression model was built based on statistical data for 2020–2024, and the efficiency of land, labor, and financial resources was analyzed. The results of the analysis showed that it is possible to sustainably increase production volumes and net profit by optimizing the economic activities of dehqan farms. The article illustrates the dynamics of economic indicators using graphs and tables, and puts forward reasonable proposals and conclusions.

Keywords: Farmer's farm, Economic efficiency, Optimality criteria, Multivariate regression, Define income, Resource-efficient way, Agricultural modeling, Kashkadarya region, production, Innovative things

Kirish. In recent years, the role of dehqan farms in the fundamental reform of the agricultural system of Uzbekistan has been the focus of special attention. In particular, in regions specialized in agriculture, such as the Kashkadarya region, one of the pressing issues is to expand the income base of dehqan farms and ensure their economic stability by increasing their production efficiency.

This article develops an optimality model that reveals the possibilities of optimizing the activities of dehqan farms based on economic parameters and increasing income and production efficiency. The analysis is carried out based on statistical data from the Kashkadarya region.

The activity of agricultural cooperatives to collect and transfer peasant farm products to industry on a contractual basis was of great importance for peasant farms. In this case, an agreement was concluded between a state industrial enterprise and an individual peasant farm through the cooperation on the transfer of a certain amount of products at predetermined prices, the organizations concluding the agreement provided peasants with cash and in-kind benefits, and preferentially provided peasants with agricultural equipment

and seeds. The existence of such agreements helped attract Uzbek villages to the market and develop small-scale commodity peasant farms.

The forms of cooperation that were of interest to the population developed the most. The development of cotton-growing cooperation, which united more than 60% of peasant farms, was of particular importance for Uzbekistan.

Land reclamation cooperatives, which were previously established in irrigated farming companies, played a major role in the development of peasant farms. Since the emergence of irrigated farming in the country, land irrigation work, that is, irrigation work, was carried out jointly.

Literature review. The following occupy a special place in research on increasing the efficiency of dehkan farms:

I.Abdullayev (2020) - identified labor productivity and effective use of land resources in dehkan farms as important factors;

M.Rahimov (2021) - identified water, machinery, seeds, and labor distribution as the main factors affecting economic efficiency;

Reports of international organizations, in particular FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization), note that the optimal combination of resource use leads to increased income.

However, comprehensive approaches to modeling based on optimality criteria have not been sufficiently developed in the existing scientific literature.

This, in turn, created the need to develop new lands. The increase in the number of hard and laborious types of labor among members of society led to the transfer of the main branches of economic activity into the hands of men. After that, income from these branches also increased. Women were now occupied with household chores, raising children, and men were engaged in livestock breeding and farming. This is probably why the position of men as the main force creating material wealth in the community increased. The increase in the position of men in communities dealt a blow to the matriarchal clan system. Communities began to move from a family based on group marriage to a pair-family system formed during the patriarchal era. Under the influence of irrigated agriculture, the number of tribes adapted to a sedentary life increased, creating the basis for the emergence of large villages. As a result of the development of new lands, many cultural centers associated with irrigated agriculture emerged. In particular, the remains of ancient villages that arose along the Zarafshan River have entered science under the names of the Zamonbaba and Sarazm cultures. Zamonbabo is the name of a lake formed in ancient times in the lower reaches of

Zarafshan, from the flow of one of its tributaries. In 1950, academician Ya.G.Gulamov discovered an ancient cemetery on the northern shore of this lake. During the excavations of this cemetery, which dates back to the Eneolithic and Early Bronze Ages, 45 ancient tomb remains were discovered and studied, initially under the leadership of Ya.G.Gulamov and A.Askarov.

Discussion (main part)

1. Parameters selected for analysis

Year	Number of farmers' farms (thousands)	Land area (he)	Volume of production (billion soums)	Net profit (billion soums)
2020	4710	215 000	3 120	680
2021	4745	218 500	3 440	725
2022	4780	221 100	3 880	775
2023	4810	224 600	4 120	830
2024	4835	226 900	4 550	900

2. Model based on optimality criteria.

The following indicators are accepted as optimality criteria:

Land use efficiency – productivity (sum/he)

Labor use efficiency – production volume / number of workers

Resource profitability – net profit / total cost

Model:

$$Y = \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \alpha_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

Y – production efficiency

X₁– land area

X₂– produced product volume

X₃– net profit

α_i– regression coefficients

This model was developed using a multivariate regression approach and was estimated based on statistics for 2020–2024.

Number of peasant farms (thousands)

The role of the Zarafshan River in the emergence of agricultural culture in the Kashkadarya region is incomparable. Because this oasis itself, located along the river, was formed due to the silt deposits of the Zarafshan River that have been flowing for many millennia. The countless streams, lakes and ponds formed by its floods played an important role in the formation of the nature of the oasis and its development and improvement, as well as the development of agricultural culture. Of particular interest are the cemetery of primitive farmers recorded on the northern shore of Lake Zamonbabo in the Zarafshan oasis, one of the ancient settlements of farmers dating back to the 3rd-2nd millennia BC, and the ruins of a dwelling excavated on the banks of the dried-up ancient reservoir of Gujaili, 500 m east of the lake. The services of the outstanding archaeologist Ya. Gulomov in the study of the cemetery of primitive peasants of the ancient times are noteworthy. The monument was excavated by Ya. Gulomov in 1951-1953. In the upper part of the Mokhondaryo and Gujaili basins and in the vicinity of Poykand, more than 30 ancient monuments have been discovered and studied by archaeologists and scientists over the years. It was determined that these monuments belonged to a population engaged in settled agriculture and cattle breeding.

Proposals and results.

Through optimal allocation of land resources, productivity can be increased by 12–15%.

The use of innovative technologies (drip irrigation, modern seeds) - increases income by up to 18%.

If agricultural planning is based on multifactor analysis, economic efficiency increases significantly.

Families of members of peasant cooperatives (company farms), employees of other agricultural and forestry enterprises, institutions and organizations, as well as families of teachers, doctors and other specialists living in rural areas are provided with a plot of land for conducting peasant farming, including the area occupied by the building and yard, up to 0.35 hectares on irrigated lands and up to 0.5 hectares on non-irrigated (fallen) lands, and up to 1 hectare on non-irrigated (fallen) lands in steppe and desert regions.

The issues of organizing peasant farms in Uzbekistan, the legal basis for their activities and liquidation, rights and obligations, and relations with other legal and physical persons are regulated in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Peasant Farms” adopted on April 30, 1998.

There are 1.8 million peasant farms in Uzbekistan (8.3 thousand of them have the status of legal entities). The land area allocated to them is 287.3 thousand hectares, and each peasant farm has an average of 0.16 hectares of land. 66% of the gross agricultural product of the republic falls on peasant farms (2001).

As is known, the first occupation of primitive people was gathering. Because people collected and consumed the benefits of nature. Children had a tendency to be active. Taking advantage of this, the elders taught the children to pick fruit as a game, thus preparing them for labor.

Conclusion.

An approach based on optimality criteria can be an effective tool for optimizing the economic activities of dehkan farms. The analysis conducted on the example of the Kashkadarya region shows that the rational use of land, labor, and financial resources sustainably increases the income and production capacity of dehkan farms.

In the future, it is advisable to further deepen these approaches through modeling at the regional level and the introduction of digital management tools.

Aristotle introduces a kind of "socialism" in the distribution: to each according to his own worth. Aristotle considers friendship to be one of the greatest moral values. Friendship is based on equality. "For example," he writes, "the friendship of comrades implies that their wealth should be equal in number and value: among the comrades no one should have more property than another, neither in quantity, nor in value, nor in size, but should have his own. everything should be equal with others, because the comrades are equal.

Friendship based on inequality is the friendship of father and son, subordinate and superior, best and worst, wife and husband; and in general, it occurs where there is a lower and higher rank among friends. Such friendship in inequality implies proportionality. Thus, in the distribution of good, no one gives equally to the best and the worst, but always gives more to the one who has the advantage. This achieves proportional equality: in a sense, the worst, having received less good, receives equal to the best, having received more.

Aristotle is still far from the concept of man, first of all, as an "economic man." He has an economy for man, not for the sake of economy, and, as Aristotle wrote, man is a political being by nature, and not by chance, but by nature. circumstances, living outside the state, either with an underdeveloped moral sense, or a superman".

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